

Explicit and mnemonic method for determining a list of prime numbers

José Antoine SÉQUEIRA

Independent Researcher, Dakar, Senegal

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-4860-1450>

Email: joansera80@gmail.com

Abstract:

Here we present a simple and original method for generating prime numbers with the formula $P(n) = 2n + 3$ and using a progressive filter for eliminating non-prime numbers. Unlike the Sieve of Eratosthenes, this approach relies on arithmetic conditions, which allows for a progressive elimination of composite integers. In addition to its pedagogical impact; the results show that this formula, accompanied by an efficient filter, generates all prime numbers greater than 2, saving time and memory.

1. Introduction

For millennia, prime numbers have fascinated mathematicians. These numbers, divisible only by 1 and themselves, seem to follow a logic that is both simple and mysterious. They appear haphazardly arranged on the number line of the set \mathbb{N} of integers. This prevents the development of an explicit formula to predict the distribution of prime numbers.

In this paper, we present a new approach to identifying even numbers that allows generating a list of prime numbers in a given interval with the formula $P(n) = 2n + 3$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The identification of these even numbers is based on progressive filtering; eliminating those that do not give prime numbers $p > 2$ with the formula. Among the classical methods for generating prime numbers, we distinguish the Sieve of Eratosthenes, known since Antiquity, as well as various probabilistic exploitation algorithms. This new approach is therefore a complementary method in a very active field of research. Especially in a world where prime numbers play a central role in number theory, cryptography and computer science.

2. Mnemonic method for finding the list of prime numbers between 0 and 100.

The program formulated by the equality $P(n) = 2n + 3$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is a formula that only generates odd numbers $P(n) \in \mathbb{N}$ greater than 1. We know that any prime number other than 2 is an odd integer; however, the converse is false. We must then define mnemonic filters on even whole numbers $2n$.

2.1 First filter

For the first filter that we are going to define is to eliminate even numbers that end with 2 that differ from the number 2. In other words, even whole numbers verifying $2n \equiv 2 \pmod{10}$. This first filter eliminates odd numbers that are multiples of 5 and different from 5.

2.2 Second filter

The second filter consists of filtering even numbers that are multiples of 3. In other words, integers verifying $2n \equiv 0 \pmod{6}$.

2.3 Even numbers $2n$ such as $0 \leq 2n < 100$ generating prime number

The even numbers $2n$ such that $0 \leq 2n < 100$ and $2n \not\equiv 2 \pmod{10}$ are $2n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{6}$:
0 ; 2 ; 4 ; 8 ; 10 ; 14 ; 16 ; 20 ; 26 ; 28 ; 34 ; 38 ; 40 ; 44 ; 46 ; 50 ; 56 ; 58 ; 64 ; 68 ;
70 ; 74 ; 76 ; 80 ; 84 ; 88 ; 94.

Which gives us the table:

2n	0	2	4	8	10	14	16	20	26	28	34	38	40	44
2n+3	3	5	7	11	13	17	19	23	29	31	37	41	43	47

2n	46	50	56	58	64	68	70	74	76	80	84	88	94
2n+3	49	53	59	61	67	71	73	77	79	83	87	91	97

This list can be determined mnemonically. The formula $P(n) = 2n + 3$ associated with the filter on even numbers $2n$; such that $2n \not\equiv 2 \pmod{10}$ and $2n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{6}$; gives all prime numbers between 0 and 100 with three exceptions 49; 77 and 91 all multiples of the prime number 7. These three numbers are generated by even numbers of the form $2n \equiv 4 \pmod{14}$. If we eliminate the even number which are of the form $2n \equiv 4 \pmod{14}$: 46; 74 and 88. We finally obtain the list of all prime numbers between 0 and 100:

2n	0	2	4	8	10	14	16	20	26	28	34	38
2n+3	3	5	7	11	13	17	19	23	29	31	37	41

2n	40	44	50	56	58	64	68	70	76	80	84	94
2n+3	43	47	53	59	61	67	71	73	79	83	87	97

3. Methodology

The method consists of determining the prime numbers p between 0 and $\sqrt{100}$ then removing the even numbers $2n \equiv p - 3 \pmod{2p}$ with $n > 0$. The advantage here is that even numbers $2n \equiv 2 \pmod{10}$ all end in 2 and those of the form $2n \equiv 0 \pmod{6}$ are multiples of 3 (so the sum of the digits is a multiple of 3).

A general method for determining prime numbers $p < N$ ($p \in \mathbb{P}$ and $N \in \mathbb{N}$):

- We start by finding the prime numbers $p_i < \sqrt{N}$

- We list the even numbers $2n$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$): $2n \not\equiv p_i - 3 \pmod{2p}$.
- We determine the prime numbers $p < N$ with the formula $P(n) = 2n + 3$; such that: $2n \not\equiv p_i - 3 \pmod{2p_i}$. We can optimize on the steps $\pmod{2p_i}$ by avoiding the steps which give the even multiples of 3 and starting with p_i^2 . This allows us to skip the multiples of p_i and of the prime numbers less than p_i . Which amounts to skipping the first one $2p$ because $p - 3 + 2p = 3p - 3$ which is a multiple of 3.

For example, if we take $p_i = 7$; we can start by eliminating the even number $49 - 3 = 46$. We jump $14 = 2 \times 7$ and start with $28 = 4 \times 7$ what allows us to eliminate the number $49 + 28 - 3 = 77 - 3 = 74$

4. Advantage

As with Eratosthenes' method, to determine the prime numbers $p < N$ we just:

- Determine the even numbers $m = 2n$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $m \leq N - 3$.
- Determine the prime numbers p_i such that: $p_i < \sqrt{N}$
- Eliminate even numbers $m = 2n$ such as: $m \equiv p_i - 3 \pmod{2p_i}$. We can optimize on the steps $\pmod{2p_i}$ by avoiding the steps which give even numbers which are multiples of 3 and starting with p_i^2

Since this approach is very similar to Eratosthenes' method, it is easier to program. In addition, prime numbers can be calculated mentally; for small intervals. The advantage of this progression is that these three steps can be performed simultaneously using a memory aid.

5. Perspectives and discussion

In our study we noticed the formula $P(n) = 2n + 3$ generates both prime numbers and non-prime numbers. The even numbers m that generate non-prime numbers are of the form $m \equiv p - 3 \pmod{2p}$. We observe steps $2p$; moreover first step and the steps of $2p = sp$ with s an even number such that $s \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ must be skipped to avoid having even numbers that are multiples of 3. With the steps of $2p$ kept; we thus obtain progressions of: $4p$; $6p = 4p + 2p$; $10p = 4p + 2p + 4p$; ...

We thus distinguish steps 4 followed by 2 followed by 4; which corresponds to sequences of 4 or 2. Can this remark make it possible to find a distribution function for non-prime numbers and to deduce a distribution function for prime numbers?

For example to eliminate multiples of the prime number 7, we will start with the even number $49 - 3 = 46$. Then we successively add: $46 + 28 = 74$; $74 + 14 = 88$ and so on. In the formula $P(n) = 2n + 3$, we will not take into account these even numbers.

This new method allows us to give a new representation of the order of all integer numbers. A way of representing the set of integers as a tree whose trunk would be made up of the set of prime numbers. From each number begins a branch formed by the multiples of this prime number. We must note that the branches formed by the prime numbers intermingle with each other at the levels of the common multiples; thus forming a closed network.

We must also point out that this method is mnemonic and from a pedagogical point of view, it is very suitable for secondary level teaching. The objective is to identify the even numbers which, associated with the formula, $P(n) = 2n + 3$ allow the exact generation of prime numbers.

6. Conclusion

In this paper we have presented a simple and mnemonic approach to generating prime numbers, based on the formula $P(n) = 2n + 3$ and a progressive filtering system. This approach illustrates a possibility of representing the structure of prime numbers by means of simple rules, while opening the way to practical applications in algorithms and cryptography.

7. Data Availability statement

All data that support this paper are included within the article.

8. Conflicts of interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding this paper.

9. Pre-print

A preprint has previously been published on Zenodo [Séqueira, J. A. (2025), link: <https://zenodo.org/records/17042349>]

10. Author contribution

José Antoine Séqueira wrote the main manuscript text, prepared all figures and tables, and then reviewed the manuscript.

11. Funding

The author did not receive support from any organization for the submitted work.

Bibliographic reference

- [1] Dimitris Koukoulopoulos (2024) Introduction to Number Theory University of Montreal Last updated: December 18, 2024 (Dimitris Koukoulopoulos (2024) Introduction à la théorie des nombres Université de Montréal Dernière mise-à-jour: 18 décembre 2024) <https://share.google/ZKOdcHuJaYgbRu1Kw>
- [2] Antoine Chambert-Loir (2025) INTEGERS AND RATIONAL NUMBERS, CONGRUENCES, PERMUTATIONS, Course at the University of Rennes1 (2004–2005) (Antoine Chambert-Loir (2025) NOMBRES ENTIERS ET RATIONNELS, CONGRUENCES, PERMUTATIONS Cours à l'Université de Rennes1 (2004–2005)) <https://share.google/plUgRBaF08xtGDpKu>
- [3] NICOL, H. Sieves of Eratosthenes. Nature 166, 565–566 (1950). <https://doi.org/10.1038/166565b0>
- [4] O'NEILL ME. The Genuine Sieve of Eratosthenes. Journal of Functional Programming.2009; 19(1):95-106.doi:10.1017/S0956796808007004 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0956796808007004>